

Metabolic Evaluation of Lupin-Enriched Yogurt by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Metabolomics

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ABSTRACT: Untargeted nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) metabolomics was used to evaluate compositional changes during yogurt fermentation upon lupin enrichment compared to traditional conditions. Lupin significantly changed the sample metabolic profile and its time course dynamics, seemingly delaying microbial action. The levels of organic and amino acids were significantly altered, along with those of some sugars, nucleotides, and choline compounds. Lupin seemed to favor acetate and formate synthesis, compared to that of citrate and fumarate; a higher formate levels may suggest increased levels of *Streptococcus thermophilus* action, compared to *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*. Lupin-yogurt was poorer in hippurate, lactose (and hence lactate), galactose, glucose-1-phosphate, and galactose-1-phosphate, containing higher orotate levels (possibly related to increased uridine derivatives), among other differences. Trigonelline was confirmed as a lupin marker, possibly together with glutamate and histidine. Other metabolite trajectories remained unchanged upon lupin addition, unveiling unaffected underlying processes. These results demonstrate the usefulness of untargeted NMR metabolomics to understand/develop new foodstuffs and their production processes, highlighting the identity of a variety of bioactive metabolites with importance for human health.

KEYWORDS: fermentation, yogurt, lupin, legumes, metabolomics, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy

1. INTRODUCTION

Yogurt is one of the most popular fermented dairy products, the consumption of which is increasing worldwide due to its unique flavor, high nutritional value, and associated health benefits (e.g., digestion enhancement, immunostimulatory effects, and anticarcinogenic and antidiabetic properties).¹ Yogurt is obtained from fermenting milk, usually using the two symbiotic species of lactic acid bacteria, *Streptococcus thermophilus* (ST) and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* (LB) as starter cultures.² In recent years, consumers have become increasingly aware of the health-related functions of foods, and this has led to a higher demand for products with improved nutritional value and health benefits. Hence, several approaches have been followed to improve yogurt, such as the inclusion/improvement of probiotics,³ and incorporation/addition of fruit and/or other plant-based ingredients.⁴ Regarding the latter, legumes appear as interesting potential ingredients due to their benefits related to reduced risk of cardiovascular diseases (e.g., obesity and type-2 diabetes), improvement of gut microbial diversity, modulation of oxidative stress and inflammatory status, and reduced risk of cancer.⁵ Lupin (*Lupinus albus*) is a pulse crop that grows in the Mediterranean region, which contains relatively high contents of protein and other nutrients such as fiber and polyunsaturated fatty acids (often missing in conventional formulations), while exhibiting beneficial antioxidant and prebiotic properties. The main antinutritional factors found in sweet lupin comprise raffinose family oligosaccharides, phytic acid, and polyphenols, in tandem with relatively low amounts of lectins and trypsin inhibitors, compared to other legumes such as cowpea, kidney

bean, and soybean.⁶ Lupin addition to yogurt has been evaluated for nutritional, rheological, and sensorial properties,⁷ having revealed beneficial effects, despite slightly undesirable sensorial characteristics (bitterness, granularity, and after-taste). Lupin-enriched yogurt was revealed to contain increased levels of protein (+40%), fiber (+90%), and omega-3 fatty acids (+353%) in relation to its natural yogurt counterpart, thus enabling differential nutritional claims (such as “high in protein”, “source of fiber”, and “source of omega-3”) and supporting previously mentioned health benefits. Furthermore, the addition of lupin enhanced yogurt texture attributes, generating a firmer, more consistent, and adhesive matrix, compared to natural yogurt.

However, only a few studies have measured detailed metabolic changes upon legume addition to foods in general. To this end, food untargeted metabolomics appears as an excellent approach for product characterization and classification based on metabolic profile.⁸ Originally applied in health-related areas, metabolomics combines high-throughput analytical information through nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy or mass spectrometry methods with multivariate statistical analysis. NMR provides simultaneous information on several different compound families, requiring

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Figure 1. 500 MHz ^1H NMR average spectra of yogurt corresponding to Pr after 6 h of fermentation for (a) control samples (traditional fermentation) and (b) lupin-enriched samples. Insets show the expanded aliphatic (δ 0.5–3.0) and aromatic regions (δ 6.0–10). Peak assignments: (1–3) aliphatic amino acids (1: isoleucine; 2: leucine; and 3: valine); (4) lactate; (5) alanine; (6) acetate; (7) *N*-acetylglucosamine; (8) glutamate; (9) pyruvate; (10) succinate; (11) citrate; (12) creatine; (13) dimethyl sulfone; (14) acetylcholine; (15) choline; (16) phosphocholine, PC; (17) glycerophosphocholine, GPC; (18) lactose; (19) galactose; (20) orotate, (21) fumarate; (22) tyrosol; (23) tyrosine; (24) phenylalanine; (25) benzoate; (26) hippurate; (27) adenosine diphosphate and/or adenosine triphosphate, ADP/ATP; (28) formate; and (29) trigonelline. The full list of identified metabolites is shown in Table S1. Visually identified spectral variations between the different yogurts are highlighted by arrows and full metabolite names in (b).

minimal sample preparation and offering rapidity and high reproducibility. The method has been applied to many foods, e.g., beer, coffee, fruit juices, olive oil, tea, vinegar, wine, and dairy products.^{8,9} In yogurt, metabolomics has been used to assess the impact of different probiotic strains, nutritionally rich constituents and different experimental/technological conditions on yogurt metabolic composition, nutritional quality, and physicochemical and organoleptic characteristics.^{3,10,11} The most studied topic has been the use of different strains with probiotic properties, the majority belonging to the *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, and *Levilactobacillus* genera.^{3,12,13} Also, different fermentation temperatures have been tested, either alone¹⁴ or combined with probiotic strains,¹⁵ anaerobic conditions,¹⁶ or high-pressure technology.¹⁰ In addition, since γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) is suggested to reduce stress, inhibit cancer cell proliferation, decrease blood pressure, and prevent diabetes, GABA-enriched yogurt has recently attracted considerable interest.¹⁷ In the case of plant- and/or fruits-based yogurts, metabolomics has studied the effects of added highland barley,¹¹ hemp seeds,¹⁸ and red-purple pitaya fruit colorant.¹⁹ Regarding legumes, and lupin in particular, the presence of antinutrient compounds⁵ makes it even more important to fully analyze the effect of incorporating such an ingredient in popular foodstuffs.

In this work, the impact of the addition of lupin during set-yogurt fermentation on the metabolic profile of yogurts was assessed by NMR metabolomics, building up on a previous report of beneficial nutritional, sensorial, and environmental impact characterization of the same product.⁷ The metabolic profiles of lupin-enriched samples were evaluated as a function of fermentation time (0, 2, 4, and 6 h and postrefrigeration,

Pr), and compared with those of yogurts produced under control conditions, providing insights into the role of lupin on fermentation biochemistry and final product composition.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Yogurt Preparation. The yogurts were prepared as described previously⁷ (Figure S1). Briefly, for all yogurts, 6% of skimmed milk powder (Molico powdered milk, 6.8 g/100 mL) was mixed with semiskimmed milk (Milhafre, Azores, Portugal). The lupin-enriched formulation included the addition of 4% dehulled organic fine-ground lupin flour (4.16 g/100 mL) (Provida, Portugal). The mixture was homogenized and heated to 90 ± 2 °C, in a Thermomix (Vorwerk, Germany), for 3.5 min. After cooling to 40 ± 2 °C, the preparation was inoculated with an organic powder preparation for yogurt (Natali, France) containing *S. thermophilus* (ST) and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* (LB) and homogenized (2 min). The fermentation step occurred for approximately 6 h (until pH of 4.6 ± 0.1 was reached), at 42 ± 2 °C, under complete rest. After fermentation, the yogurts were cooled down and maintained at 4 °C for 24 h (refrigeration step, Figure S1), after which the samples were stored at -80 °C, until analysis. Overall, a total of 30 samples were obtained (15 controls and 15 lupin-enriched samples) distributed by five different time intervals during fermentation (0, 2, 4, and 6 h and Pr, with $n = 3$ per time point). Each sample (30–50 g) was immediately stored at -80 °C.

2.2. NMR Spectroscopy. For NMR analysis, yogurt samples were prepared as described in a previous report.²⁰ Briefly, after thawing, 10 g of each yogurt sample was centrifuged (6500g, 10 min, room temperature). After centrifugation, 4 mL of the supernatant was collected, again centrifuged (6500g, 10 min, room temperature) and left to precipitate overnight at 4 °C. Three mL of the supernatant were filtered (acetate membrane, ϕ 0.22 μm) yielding ca. 1.5 mL of sample. The filtered samples were dried under a vacuum and stored at -80 °C until NMR analysis.

Figure 2. Multivariate statistical analysis of the ^1H NMR spectra of yogurts produced under control conditions (blue, C, CTR) and with lupin enrichment (red, L, LUP), throughout the fermentation process. Symbols corresponding to fermentation time: 0 h (*); 2 h (●); 4 h (▲); 6 h (◆); and Pr (◇). Scores scatter plots for (a) PCA and (b) PLS-DA. R^2X : fraction of the variation of X -variables explained by the model; R^2Y : fraction of the variation of Y -variables explained by the model; and Q^2 , predictive power. Abbreviations: LV, latent variables; PC, principal components.

For analysis, the extracts were reconstituted using 700 μL of deuterated 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 7.4, containing 0.25% sodium 3-trimethylsilyl-2,2,3,3- d_4 -propionate (TSP) for chemical shift referencing. The mixture was then vortexed, centrifuged (8000g, 10 min, room temperature), and a total volume of 550 μL was transferred into 5 mm NMR tubes. All NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE III 500 spectrometer (Bruker, Rheinstetten, Germany) operating at 500.13 MHz frequency for ^1H observation, equipped with a 5 mm TXI, at 298 K. For each sample, a standard 1D ^1H NMR spectrum was recorded using the *noesypr1d* pulse program (Bruker library) with 2.3 s of acquisition time, 4 s relaxation delay, 512 scans, 7002.8 Hz spectral width, and 32 k data points. Each free-induction decay was zero-filled to 64 k points and multiplied by a 0.3 Hz exponential line-broadening function prior to Fourier transform. Spectra were manually phased, baseline corrected, and chemical shift referenced to the TSP signal (δ 0.0). 2D NMR spectra ($^1\text{H}/^1\text{H}$ total correlation, TOCSY, $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$ heteronuclear single quantum correlation, HSQC, and J -resolved) were recorded to aid spectral assignment. Peak assignment was also based in existing literature^{12,13,20,21} and spectral databases, namely, Bruker BIOREF-CODE, the FooDB project (www.foodb.ca, accessed in 10–05–2023), the human metabolome (HMDB),²² and the Chenomx Profiler SOFTWARE (Chenomx NMR Suite 7.5, Chenomx Inc., Edmonton, Canada).

2.3. Statistical Analysis. For multivariate analysis (MVA), the full resolution (1D) ^1H NMR spectra were converted into data matrices (AMIX-viewer 3.9.14, Bruker Biospin, Rheinstetten, Germany), excluding the suppressed water region (δ 4.77–4.83). Spectra were aligned using recursive segment-wise peak alignment (Matlab 8.3.0, The MathWorks Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, USA).²³ Since the overall spectral profile changed significantly during fermentation due to changes in intense and broad lipid signals and thus affecting total spectral area (Figure S2), spectra were normalized using the probabilistic quotient normalization (PQN),²⁴ taking the average of all spectra for 0 h of fermentation as reference (PQN normalization was carried out using Matlab 8.3.0, the MathWorks Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, USA). Principal component analysis (PCA) and partial-least-squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) were applied, upon unit variance (UV) scaling (SIMCA P11.5, Umetrics, Umea, Sweden) and models were considered robust for predictive power (Q^2) values approaching or above 0.5. The MVA results were visualized through factorial coordinates (score plots) and factorial contributions (loading plots). The loading plots were back transformed by multiplying each variable by its standard deviation and colored according to each variable importance to the projection (VIP) value (Matlab 8.3.0, The MathWorks Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, USA). For each identified metabolite or relevant resonance, peak

areas were integrated in the raw spectra (AMIX-viewer 3.9.14, Bruker Biospin, Rheinstetten, Germany) and normalized by PQN. For each pairwise comparison, effect size (ES) values²⁵ (considering IESL values >2.0 of relevant magnitude) and statistical significance (p -values) were assessed by the Wilcoxon test (R software, version 4.0.0, combined with R-studio version 1.3.1093, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). The Benjamini and Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR)²⁶ correction was applied for multiple testing.

3. RESULTS

3.1. ^1H NMR Spectra of Yogurts. The average ^1H NMR spectrum of control yogurts (PrC, Figure 1a) reflects the high complexity of the samples in terms of the metabolite composition. Peak assignment unveiled a total of 44 metabolites (Table S1), comprising: 12 organic acids; 13 amino acids and derivatives; and 7 sugars and derivatives, including uridine derivative UDP-galactose to add to other 4 nucleotides and derivatives [adenosine monophosphate and/or triphosphate (ADP/ATP), uridine and uridine monophosphate (UMP)]; choline, glycerophosphocholine (GPC), and phosphocholine (PC); and other metabolites (namely, acetoin, acetylcarnitine, dimethylsulfone, and tyrosol). This set of identified compounds is broadly consistent with previous NMR studies of yogurts^{12,13} and milk products in general.²⁰

The average ^1H NMR spectrum registered for control conditions (Figure 1a) is dominated by resonances arising from sugar metabolites, particularly lactose (peaks 18 and 19) and galactose (peaks 19) and lactate (peak 4). Visual comparison with the spectrum of lupin-enriched yogurt reveals the presence of the same set of compounds detected (with the exception of trigonelline, as discussed below) but at distinct relative levels (Figure 1b). Inspection unveils apparent lower amounts of lactose (peaks 18) and galactose (peaks 19); citrate, fumarate, hippurate, and lactate, although the latter peak is cutoff in Figure 1 (peaks 11, 21, and 26 and 4, respectively); and higher amounts of ADP/ATP (peaks 27) (Figure 1b). Notably, trigonelline (peak 29, Figure 1b), an alkaloid plant hormone found in several seeds and seedlings of legumes, including lupin,²⁷ was only detected in lupin-enriched yogurts. Additionally, some still unassigned resonances between ca. δ 5.0–6.2 (Figure 1b) were clearly increased in lupin-enriched yogurts. However, all of the above visual

Figure 3. Organic acid trajectories throughout the fermentation process (from 0 h to Pr) for control (in blue) and lupin-enriched (in red) yogurts. From (a) to (k): acetate, benzoate, citrate, formate, fumarate, hippurate, lactate, malonate, orotate, 2-oxoglutarate, pyruvate, and succinate. Dashed boxes for measurements in Pr identify statistically significant differences between control and lupin-enriched yogurts. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; and *** $p < 0.001$ express statistical relevance between a time point and the preceding one.

changes between the two final products require statistical evaluation, as discussed below.

3.2. Multivariate Analysis of Control and Lupin-Enriched Yogurts. PCA of the ^1H NMR spectra of all control samples (Figure 2, left, blue symbols, positive PC2) revealed a gradual profile change up to 4 h, with a subsequent overlap of 6 h and PrC samples. Similar results were observed for lupin-enriched samples (Figure 2, left, red symbols, negative PC1), although their clear separation from control samples, in both PCA and PLS-DA scores plots (Figure 2, left and right, respectively), indicates that significantly distinct profiles characterize each group of samples.

In both groups, the major differences observed between 0, 2, and 4 h samples in the full models (Figure 2) were clearly confirmed by PCA and PLS-DA of each group separately (Figure S3a,b), which also illustrates higher sample heterogeneity at 0 and 2 h. In the loadings plot (Figure S3c) corresponding to the PLS-DA model of lupin-enriched samples (Figure S3b, right), a set of positive broad resonances identifies lipids,²⁸ as more abundant in 0 and 2 h samples (in positive PC1/LV1), compared to the remaining samples. Indeed, a gradual decrease in lipid resonances is clearly seen in the spectra of the 0 to 2 to 4 h samples, not only of lupin-enriched samples but also of control samples (Figure S3). In addition, in the same loadings plot (Figure S3c), the negative loadings profile indicates higher abundance of many metabolites (numbered as in shown in Figure 1) at 4, 6 h, and PrC, including lactate (peaks 4) and sugars, among others. Furthermore, some compositional changes seem to be induced by refrigeration, particularly in control samples, for which PrC samples show some separation from 6 h samples in PCA (Figure S3a).

3.3. Metabolic Changes during Fermentation of Control Yogurt.

Fermentation under control conditions is accompanied by changes in a total of 33 compounds, including many organic acids and amino acids, some sugars, nucleotide derivatives, choline compounds, and other metabolites (Table S2). Changes are expressed in ES (Table S2) and represented in normalized area trajectories, as a function of time in Figures 3–5. The changes noted between 0 and 2 h are the most significant, both in magnitude and significance (note that most variations remain significant upon FDR correction; asterisks in Table S2). Less number/magnitude of changes occur from 2 to 6 h (with the 4–6 h period appearing almost eventless), followed by a large set of changes upon refrigeration.

Regarding organic acids, changes include major initial increases in lactate (effect size, ES = 34), followed by hippurate (ES = 11) and formate (ES = 10) (Table S2). Indeed, a general increase is observed in several organic acids, although with distinct dynamics (Figure 3, blue trace; and Table S2): (i) steady increases in benzoate and lactate, (ii) citrate, hippurate, orotate, pyruvate, and succinate reaching a plateau at 2 h, and (iii) formate and fumarate reaching maximum values at 4 h. Acetate, malonate, and 2-oxoglutarate show little variation throughout the process. Refrigeration leads to increases in most of the acids detected, with ES ranging between 2.3 (formate) and 7.1 (benzoate), except for citrate, hippurate, and pyruvate, which do not vary (Table S2).

The levels of amino acids (and their derivatives) also increase from 0 to 2 h of fermentation [namely, betaine, creatine, creatinine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine; ES ranging from 2.1 (creatinine) to 7.9 (betaine)], with betaine subsequently returning to the lower initial levels (Figure 4 and Table S2). In addition, alanine, isoleucine, and valine

Figure 4. Amino acids and derivatives and sugar metabolites trajectories throughout the fermentation process (from 0 h to Pr) for control (in blue) and lupin-enriched (in red) yogurts. From (a) to (j) amino acids and derivatives: alanine, betaine, creatine, creatinine, glutamate, isoleucine, histidine, phenylalanine, tyrosine, and valine; from (k) to (q) sugars and derivatives: α -glucose, glucose-1-phosphate (G1P), galactose, galactose-1-phosphate (GalIP), lactose, *N*-acetylglucosamine, and uridine diphosphate-galactose (UDP-galactose). Dashed boxes for measurements in Pr identify statistically significant differences between control and lupin-enriched yogurts. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; and *** $p < 0.001$ express statistical relevance between a time point and the preceding one.

decrease up to 4 h (Figure 4). As observed for organic acids, amino acids are not seen to vary significantly from 4 to 6 h, whereas most amino acids increase again upon refrigeration, ranging between $ES = 1.9$ (betaine) and 4.7 (phenylalanine) (Table S2 and Figure 4). Regarding sugars, a notable increase in galactose is observed at 2 h ($ES = 63$) (Table S2 and Figure 4) and then increases slightly along with lactose, although the latter showed no significance (Figure 4). Decreases are observed in glucose-1-phosphate (G1P) ($ES = -2.2$), galactose-1-phosphate (GalIP) ($ES = -2.6$), and UDP-galactose ($ES = 5.0$) (Table S2 and Figure 4), although again no significant changes take place from 4 to 6 h. Upon refrigeration, a small increase in the level of galactose is noted ($ES = 2.2$).

Other changes during fermentation in controls include (i) significant increases in choline, glycerophosphocholine (GPC) and phosphocholine (PC), acetylcarnitine, dimethylsulfone, and tyrosol (ES ranging between 1.8, for acetylcarnitine, and

4.5, for tyrosol), (ii) a qualitative decrease in uridine, and (iii) some variations in ADP/ATP (fluctuation) and acetoin (decrease) (Table S2 and Figure 5). Regarding these compounds, refrigeration is accompanied by decreased uridine ($ES = -2.4$) and increased acetoin, dimethylsulfone, and tyrosol (ES in 2.3–3.3 range).

3.4. Metabolic Changes during Fermentation of Lupin-Enriched Yogurt. In lupin-enriched samples, a total of 23 compounds show changes during the fermentation process, interestingly revealing a distinct behavior over time compared to controls (Table S3). In terms of organic acids, initial (2 h) increases in formate ($ES = 5.0$), fumarate ($ES = 6.6$) and lactate ($ES = 8.4$) were observed (whereas no marked increases occurred in controls), to which increases in benzoate and orotate at 4 h ($ES = 3.1$), and succinate at 6 h ($ES = 2.2$) are added. Inspection of metabolite trajectories (Figure 3) shows that acetate and formate levels are consistently maintained above those in controls, whereas lupin-enriched

Figure 5. Nucleotides derivatives, choline, and other metabolites trajectories throughout the fermentation process (from 0 h to Pr) for control (in blue) and lupin-enriched (in red) yogurts. From (a) to (c) nucleosides and derivatives: uridine, adenosine diphosphate and/or triphosphate (ADP/ATP), and uridine monophosphate (UMP); from (d) to (f) choline metabolites: choline, glycerophosphocholine (GPC), and phosphocholine; and from (g) to (k) other metabolites: acetoin, acetylcarnitine, dimethylsulfone, tyrosol, and trigonelline. ^a The acetoin peak was not integrated at 0 h due to the major overlap with lipid resonances; [#] is only present in lupin-enriched samples. Dashed boxes for measurements in Pr identify statistically significant differences between control and lupin-enriched yogurts. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; and *** $p < 0.001$ express statistical relevance between a time point and the preceding one.

samples are less concentrated in citrate, fumarate, hippurate, and lactate (confirming visual spectral observations, Figure 1). Broadly overlapping trajectories between controls and lupin-enriched samples are noted for benzoate, malonate, orotate (although tending to higher levels in lupin samples), 2-oxoglutarate, and pyruvate (Figure 3). Contrary to controls, more changes take place from 4 to 6 h with only formate (ES = -3.9) and fumarate (ES = 2.3) varying with refrigeration (Table S3).

In relation to amino acids and derivatives, the general increase observed in controls is replaced by initial (2 h) variations in both directions in a smaller set of amino acids, followed by a general uptake of alanine, betaine, isoleucine, and valine at 4 h (ES between -2.9 , for betaine, and -8.4 , for isoleucine) and of phenylalanine at 6 h (ES = -5.3) (Table S3). No amino acid changes are induced upon refrigeration, again contrary to the general increase noted in the controls (Table S3). Trajectory graphs (Figure 4) illustrate consistently lower levels of creatine, creatinine, and phenylalanine (and to a lesser extent, isoleucine, tyrosine, and valine), whereas higher levels of glutamate and histidine characterize lupin samples from 0 h. In relation to sugars, lupin-enriched samples show a much-attenuated galactose increase, compared to controls, in tandem with an increase in lactose (from 2 to 4 h, ES = 12.3), reaching a plateau of lower levels compared to controls (Figure 4 and Table S3). Lupin-enriched samples are characterized by lower levels of galactose, lactose (confirming visual observations), and, to lesser extents, of G1P, Gal1P, and *N*-acetylglucosamine; conversely, higher stable UDP-galactose

levels are found in lupin-enriched samples (Figure 4). Other compounds show relative increases at 2 h, such as uridine, ADP/ATP, and UMP, which are kept at higher levels, compared to controls. Other significant differences include higher levels of tyrosol, the presence of trigonelline (only detected in lupin samples) (Figure 5) and no influence of refrigeration on these compounds (leaving fumarate, formate, and PC as the only varying metabolites during that final step).

Indeed, the effect of refrigeration is a significantly distinct feature of lupin samples (composition hardly changes) relative to controls (generally increase in a large set of metabolites). Further direct comparison of the two end-products (Figures 3–5, dashed boxes at time point Pr, and Table S4) shows that lupin-enriched yogurt differs from traditional yogurt, by higher amounts of acetate, formate, glutamate, histidine, UDP-galactose, uridine, ADP/ATP, UMP, acetoin, tyrosol, and presence of trigonelline. The same samples have relatively lower contents of citrate, fumarate, hippurate, lactate, malonate, 2-oxoglutarate, amino acids and sugars in general (except for glutamate, histidine, and UDP-galactose), GPC and PC, acetylcarnitine, and dimethylsulfone.

4. DISCUSSION

The traditional yogurt-making process involves milk fermentation promoted by symbiotic *S. thermophilus* (ST) and *L. bulgaricus* (LB) bacterial starter cultures, known to promote the conversion of lactose into lactic acid (fermentation), hydrolysis of milk caseins into peptides and free amino acids (proteolysis), and breakdown of milk fat into free fatty acids

Figure 6. Putative metabolic relationships between altered metabolites in lupin-enriched samples ($p < 0.05$), as a function of fermentation time: (i) top colored bar expresses variations between consecutive time points (or trajectories), 4 squares for 0–2, 2–4, 4–6, and 6 h-Pr; and bottom colored bar expresses differences between L and C samples at each time point, 5 squares for 0, 2, 4, and 6 h and Pr. Box color indicates variation direction: red, decrease; green, increased. Metabolites detected by NMR are shown in bold. Red arrows show pathways specifically influenced by ST or LB activity. Abbreviations: AA, amino acid; BCAA, branched chain amino acid; CoA, coenzyme A; DMS, dimethylsulfone; ECM, extracellular medium; GIP, glucose-1-phosphate; GalIP, galactose-1-phosphate; G6P, glucose-6-phosphate; LB, *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*; PtdCho, phosphatidylcholine; UDP-Gal, uridine diphosphate-galactose; ST, *Streptococcus thermophilus*, TCA, tricarboxylic acid; three-letter code used for amino acids; and other abbreviations as defined in the caption of Figure 1.

(lipolysis).^{12,15} Our results show that, in the presence of lupin, the complex interplay of the above processes is significantly distinct, in terms of both metabolic dynamics and profile.

Regarding dynamics, it is interesting that control conditions involve many changes between 0 and 2 h with almost no changes in the 4–6 h period, followed by a final set of (weaker) changes upon refrigeration. On the contrary, in the presence of lupin, metabolite changes spread over the whole 6 h period, with refrigeration having hardly any impact in the final product composition. This interesting dynamic distinction suggests that bacterial biochemistry kinetics is significantly affected (delayed) in the presence of lupin with refrigeration not affecting end-product composition. We suggest that the apparently delayed kinetics may relate to the presence of antimicrobial compounds or metabolic inhibitors related to lupin, either present in its constitution (as is the case of trigonelline) or formed during fermentation (although the contribution of possible small differences in pH or final viable cell numbers may not be ruled out at this stage).

In relation to the biochemical profile, control conditions lead to the expected increase in lactate, resulting from the fermentation of lactose by both ST and LB cultures. The high levels of lactose remain practically unchanged (as viewed by NMR), as this disaccharide composes ca. 6.5% of yogurt and is expected to decrease progressively to about 4.2%, during fermentation.²⁹ Lactose is converted into glucose and galactose during fermentation.³⁰ It seems, however, that glucose is the main glycolysis substrate, rather than galactose (which increases), to form pyruvate and then lactate as well as

formate and acetate (Figure 6). Indeed, since most ST strains and LB strains are known to be unable to ferment galactose,³⁰ this sugar is expected to accumulate in the yogurt matrix^{21,30} and/or follow on to UDP-galactose formation to support exopolysaccharide synthesis^{15,30} (Figure 6). The slightly lower levels of glucose, intermediates GIP and GalIP, and galactose in lupin yogurt may arise from the lower lactose content in these samples. However, none of these sugar variations were reflected in changes in total carbohydrate content (lupin-enriched yogurt, 9.3 g/100 g; and control yogurt, 8.9 g/100 g),⁷ which may be determined mainly by polysaccharides. As identical quantities/types of milk were used, the lower lactose content in lupin samples could tentatively be explained by a higher retention of the disaccharide within the lupin-derived polysaccharides matrices (fiber) and/or protein moieties present in lupin (this would also be consistent with the reported higher viscosity of lupin-yogurt⁷). The increase in lactose levels observed from 2 to 4 h in lupin yogurt may indicate the breakdown of those polysaccharides or protein matrixes, coincidentally with that of lipids (observed to occur from 2 to 4 h), resulting in higher availability of lactose compared to 0 h (but still lower than control levels). We also propose that the lower galactose levels in lupin yogurt may also partially arise from a concomitant enhanced production of UDP-galactose (higher levels in lupin yogurt).

Besides conversion to lactate, pyruvate can be further converted into citrate, and particularly due to ST action, into acetate, formate, acetaldehyde, acetoin, and diacetyl.²¹ In lupin yogurt, acetate, and formate synthesis seems to be favored in

relation to citrate and fumarate synthesis. We suggest that the ST/LB mechanisms leading to citrate and fumarate formation may be inhibited by lupin components, thus leading to significant depletion of those acids. As fumarate and malate (not detected in this work) are known to be metabolized into succinate by LB strains,³¹ it is interesting to note that despite the lower levels of fumarate in lupin yogurt, succinate levels remain similar to controls, probably supported by an alternative source. Conversely, formate levels are greatly enhanced in lupin yogurt. Formate can be produced from pyruvate through the action of ST, whereas LB cannot produce formate and, instead, employs it for growth.³¹ This is the result of ST/LB protooperation, which leads to carbon dioxide, folate, pyruvate, and formate formation through ST, and release of peptides and amino acids through the proteolytic action of LB^{21,31} (Figure 6). The higher formate levels in lupin yogurt may indicate an enhanced ST action, compared to that of LB. This would be consistent with the more modest increases in creatine, creatinine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine, until 6 h, after which a formate decrease during refrigeration may indicate that LB is using this organic acid faster than ST can produce it. Still regarding organic acids, benzoate increases with fermentation in both yogurt types, although involving slightly lower levels in lupin yogurt, up to 4 h. Benzoate is an antimicrobial and antifungal agent, which is produced by lactic bacteria during fermentation, and which plays a critical role in the stability of fermented milk qualities during storage.³² As hippurate is a precursor of benzoate, the lower hippurate levels in lupin yogurt (perhaps again due to its retention within heavily hydrogen-bonded polysaccharide matrixes) may explain the slightly lower benzoate levels, although not compromising the benzoate content in the end-product. Orotate is an intermediate in pyrimidine biosynthesis,²⁰ and its increased levels in lupin yogurt are likely to relate to the enhanced levels of uridine (although slightly decreased with refrigeration), UMP and UDP-galactose.

Regarding amino acids and derivatives, LB proteolytic action in controls may be particularly responsible for the noted increases in betaine (from 0 to 2 h), creatine, creatinine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine. Indeed, it has been reported that increased levels of aromatic amino acids may be related to protein degradation.³³ The general progression of amino acid levels is similar between controls and lupin yogurts, although the latter contain lower relative levels of creatine, creatinine, and phenylalanine (and to a lesser extent, isoleucine, tyrosine, and valine). This may corroborate the decreased LB proteolytic action, as suggested above. In addition, refrigeration seems to enhance amino acid levels in controls but not in lupin-containing samples, an interesting observation that will require further investigation. We further suggest that lupin-enriched yogurts are enriched in glutamate and histidine from 0 h due to their presence in lupin (such amino acids show, however, no dependence on fermentation time). In fact, glutamate has been reported as the most abundant amino acid in lupin.³⁴ Finally, the early alanine, isoleucine, and valine decreases noted in both yogurt types may relate to their anaplerotic use feeding the tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA) for ATP production,³⁵ particularly by ST bacteria.³⁶ Alanine is also known to be used in peptidoglycan synthesis, whereas branched chain amino acids such as isoleucine and valine are important substrates for both strains and, thus, expected to be taken up early in fermentation. In addition, amino acid conversion to flavor-compounds may be occurring through

deamidation and decarboxylation to produce α -ketoacids. These can be further metabolized to alcohols, esters, and acids.³⁷ Such end-products were, however, not detected in the NMR spectra, perhaps due to their low concentrations.

Similar behavior was noted for the two yogurt types with regard to the remaining compounds detected. Namely, a similar behavior is seen for choline compounds (increasing tendency, particularly at initial fermentation times), with higher levels of choline having been related to disruption of casein micelles³⁸ and storage conditions.²⁰ The decrease in acetoin, equivalent for both yogurt types, may reflect a similar change for valine. Indeed, a study of ST fermentation using L-valine as a supplement in soymilk whey showed that enhanced acetoin production from α -acetolactate occurred, rather than through nonenzymatic oxidation from α -acetolactate to diacetyl.³⁹ Other similar features for both types of yogurts include acetylcarnitine and dimethylsulfone (both slightly increased), which respectively should reflect fatty acid transport and oxidation⁴⁰ (as shown to occur in the 0–4 h period of fermentation) and the catabolism of sulfur amino acids, in particular methionine.⁴¹ Finally, our results have confirmed the alkaloid hormone trigonelline as a recognized indicator of lupin addition,²⁷ a metabolite which regulates plant cell cycle functions, nodulation, and oxidative stress, thus generally supporting plant survival and growth.⁴² Interestingly, trigonelline is seen to increase slightly at 4 h, probably due to initial hydrophilic retention within biopolymeric matrixes.

In summary, for the first time, to our knowledge, untargeted metabolomics (using NMR) revealed detailed compositional changes taking place during yogurt fermentation in the presence of added lupin flour compared to traditional control conditions. Our results unveiled that the use of lupin flour significantly changes the complex interplay of ongoing biochemical processes, as reflected in terms of the evolution of the metabolic profile over time. Specifically, in the presence of lupin, metabolic changes seem to reflect an apparent delayed microbial action (with refrigeration not impacting on end-product composition), accompanied by significant changes in the levels of specific organic acids, amino acids, some sugars, nucleotides, and choline compounds. In particular, lupin seems to favor acetate and formate synthesis, compared to that of citrate and fumarate, consistently with higher levels of *S. thermophilus* action, relatively to *L. bulgaricus*. In addition, further observations indicated that lupin-yogurt is poorer in hippurate, lactose (and lactate), galactose, glucose-1-phosphate, and galactose-1-phosphate, while containing higher orotate and trigonelline (lupin marker) levels, among other differences. This detailed compositional knowledge adds to previously reported beneficial nutritional and rheological properties of lupin-yogurt (although a slightly undesirable sensorial profile was noted), supporting additional benefits of the presence of specific bioactive metabolites and supporting possible further developments of a new lupin-enriched yogurt.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Data Availability Statement

The data presented in this study will be submitted to the Metabolomics Workbench database and ID information will be provided in due time.

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jafc.3c05837>.

List of compounds and corresponding spin systems identified in 500 MHz ^1H NMR spectra of the yogurts under study, ES values of varying metabolites ($p < 0.05$) identified in control samples (traditional fermentation conditions) as a function of time, ES values of varying metabolites ($p < 0.05$) identified in lupin-enriched samples as a function of time, ES values of varying metabolites ($p < 0.05$) in yogurts produced with lupin-enrichment and postrefrigeration (PrL) compared to those produced under control conditions (PrC), general workflow of the production of control and lupin-enriched yogurts and selected sampling time points for NMR metabolomics, spectral expansions of the aliphatic (0.8–2.5 ppm) and sugar (5.0–5.5 ppm) regions of the 500 MHz ^1H NMR spectra of samples produced with lupin enrichment and under control conditions as a function of fermentation time, PCA and PLS-DA obtained with ^1H NMR spectra of control samples (blue, C) and lupin-enriched samples (red, L), and LV1 loadings plot (colored according to VIP) corresponding to the PLS-DA model (PDF)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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